

eggs was recorded. Potted MR7 rice plants were used as control. Oviposition occurred on only three

of the seven species tested (see table). The highest oviposition and hatchability were observed in *Echinochloa crus-galli*.

The mirid did not oviposit on *Setaria geniculata*, *Sacciolepis indica*, *Eleusine indica*, or *Paspalum conjugatum*. □

Parasites of white rice leafhopper *Cofana spectra* (Dist.) [Hemiptera: Cicadellidae] in the Philippines

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Numbers and kinds of parasites attacking the egg, nymphal, and adult stages of *Cofana spectra* (Distant) were recorded

Egg parasitization (%) Eggs exposed in field (no./date)

Abundance of white rice leafhopper *Cofana spectra* (Dist.) in rice field, light trap collections, and parasitization of eggs, nymphs, or adults. IRRI, 1982 wet season.

during the 1982 wet season at IRRI. Potted rice plants infested with white rice leafhopper eggs laid by a greenhouse colony were set in a rice field each week 29–98 days after transplanting. Four species of egg parasites were recovered, the most prevalent of which was a mymarid — *Gonatocerus cingulatus* Perkins — that parasitized up to 17% of eggs (see figure). *Anagrus flaveolus* Waterhouse, *A. optabilis* (Parkins) (Mymaridae), and *Paracentrobia* sp. (Trichogrammatidae) parasitized less than 6% of eggs.

White rice leafhopper nymphs and adults were parasitized by a strepsipteron — *Halictophagus spectrus* Yang — and an unidentified mite of the family Erythracidae. The parasites were recovered from nymphs and adults collected from fields

by sweep net and from live adults collected in a walk-in light trap. The strepsipteron parasitized 40–60% of nymphs and adults collected in the field, but parasitized less than 15% of adults collected from the light trap, perhaps indicating that parasitized hoppers are those less capable of flying. The mite occurred less consistently on hopper nymphs and adults but parasitized up to 23% of adults collected in the light trap.

The most prevalent parasites of white rice leafhopper — *G. cingulatus*, *H. spectrus*, and the unidentified mite — do not attack the other commonly occurring rice leafhoppers and planthoppers. The egg parasites *A. flaveolus* and *A. optabilis* are most common on the brown planthopper. *Paracentrobia* sp. has a wide host range. □

Pest management and control WEEDS

Weed control in direct-seeded upland rice

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Ten herbicides were evaluated for control of weeds in upland rice at the Malan Rice Research Station during the 1977 wet season. Soil was loamy with pH 5.8; 544 kg N, 41 kg P, and 265 K available per ha; and 0.593% organic carbon. Average

annual rainfall was 2,500 mm. Weeds were 14% *Echinochloa* spp., 22% other grasses, 23% *Cyperus* spp., and 41% broadleaf weeds.

Himdhan was drilled at 100 kg seed/ha in rows spaced at 20 cm. Before sowing, 40 kg each of P and K were applied. N at 100 kg/ha was applied in 3 splits at sowing, tillering, and panicle initiation. All herbicides (see table) were sprayed 6 days after sowing.

Hand weeding controlled weeds best

Effect of weed control treatments on rice grain yield, contributory yield characters, weed dry weight, and toxicity to rice plants. ^a

Treatment	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	1000-grain (g)	Toxicity ^b 25 DS	Dry wt of weeds (g/m ²)
Diethatyl	1	2 ef	167 c	89 b	24 cd	4.4 a	157 b
Butachlor	2	3 bc	156 c	107 a	25 abc	3.9 a	98 ef
Butralin	2	3 b	195 c	85 b	25 abc	1.9 c	122 cd
Piperophosl 2,4-D	2	4 a	320 ab	106 a	26 abc	1.5 c	86 f
Dinitramine	1	4 a	319 ab	110 a	27 ab	1.5 c	83 f
X 150	4	2 ef	167 c	79 bc	24 cd	2.3 bc	147 b
Oxadiazon	1	2 de	176 c	85 b	23 d	2.3 bc	125 cd
Pendimethalin	2	3 cd	189 c	82 bc	24 bcd	1.9 c	138 bc
Oxyfluorfen	2	2 f	172 c	84 b	24 cd	3.6 ab	115 de

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(see table), followed by dinitramine, piperophos/2,4-D, propanil, and butachlor which provided statistically comparable control.

More panicles/m² were recorded for hand weeding, but results were similar to those with dinitramine and piperophos/2,4-D. Spikelets per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, and yield followed a similar trend. Diethatyl, butachlor, and oxy-fluorfen were most toxic to the crop. □

Table continued.

Treatment	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	1000-grain (g)	Toxicity ^b 25 DS	Dry wt of weeds (g/m ²)
Propanil	3	3 b	299 b	107 a	26 ab	1.6 c	90 f
Hand weeding	25 & 50 DS	4 a	352 a	112 a	27 a	1.0 c	60 g
Unweeded control	–	2 f	153 c	68 c	23 d	1.0 c	453 a

^aIn a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bToxicity rating: 1 = no toxicity, 10 = complete kill, DS = days after sowing.

Soil and crop management

Dry matter yield reduction caused by sulfur-coated urea application to low percolation soils

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Sulfur-coated urea (SCU) is a slow-release nitrogen (N) fertilizer which, when broadcast and incorporated before transplanting, can minimize N losses and improve N efficiency in lowland rice. However, soil texture, CEC, and percolation rate affect SCU efficiency. We studied the effect of SCU on dry matter yields and micro-nutrient concentration in rice plants in soils with and without good percolation.

The greenhouse experiment in 1982 kharif was on a sandy loam Typic Ustochrept with pH 8.5, EC 0.15 mmho/cm,

0.23% organic carbon, and 4.54 meq/100 g CEC. Ten-liter pots were filled with 8 kg of air-dried, sieved soil treated with 26 mg P and 50 mg K/kg. Soil was flooded, puddled, and treated with 115 mg N/kg as prilled urea splits (PUS), urea supergranule (USG), urea mudball (MBU), or SCU. USG and MBU were deep-placed at 5-7 cm. SCU was broadcast and incorporated at 5-7 cm. Four 27-day-old PR106 seedlings were planted in each pot. Pots were flooded to maintain 5 cm standing water. Percolation for appropriate pots was maintained at 5 mm/h using pinchcocks. Treatments were in a completely randomized design with three replications. Plants were harvested at 15, 30, 45, and 60 days after transplanting (DT) and dry matter yields were recorded. Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu concentrations were determined for plants harvested at

60 DT.

Without percolation, dry matter yields, except at 15 DT, were less for SCU-treated plants than for PUS, MBU, and USG. With percolation, SCU-treated plants yielded significantly more dry matter at 60 DT than USG (Table 1). Dry matter yields from PUS and MBU equaled those from SCU.

Without percolation, SCU-treated plants generally had lower Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu concentrations than other treatments (Table 2). With percolation, they had significantly higher Fe and Mn concentrations than USG. Plants with SCU, PUS, and MBU had similar Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu concentrations. In the absence of percolation, sulfides of these metals or H₂S may have been formed and thus hindered micronutrient uptake and reduced dry matter yields. □

Table 1. Effect of percolation and urea fertilizer on rice dry matter yields.^a

Urea fertilizer	Dry matter yield at indicated days after transplanting (DT)									
	Without percolation					With percolation				
	g/hill				g/pot 60 DT	g/hill				g/pot 60 DT
15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT	15 DT		30 DT	45 DT	60 DT		
No N check	0.20	0.70	1.30	3.7	9.8 a	0.30	0.90	3.10	6.3	17.2 a
Prilled urea 3-split	0.50	2.95	5.90	17.6	37.2 c	0.50	2.20	6.10	15.0	36.3 b
Urea mudball	0.25	2.70	7.50	17.3	36.4 c	0.45	2.60	5.80	16.5	32.8 b
Urea supergranule	0.40	2.80	8.40	19.2	40.3 c	0.30	1.20	4.50	10.7	21.2 a
Sulfur-coated urea	0.35	1.80	4.30	12.5	29.3 b	0.25	2.20	5.50	18.7	32.9 b
Interaction ^b	–	–	–	–	(PXU)**	–	–	–	–	(PXU)**
CV (%)					9.9					9.9

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$, ^b** = significant at $P = 0.01$. P = percolation, U = urea material.